

Patient preferences for treatment and provider characteristics in outpatient psychotherapy: Results from a discrete choice experiment

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Hintergrund: For several years, prevalence of mental disorders and demand for psychotherapy have increased, posing a constant challenge to the mental health care system. At the same time, high rates of non-adherence and treatment dropout indicate inefficient resource allocation. Understanding patients' psychotherapy choice can inform policy makers and positively influence treatment adherence, leading to improved treatment outcomes and patient satisfaction.

Zielsetzung: The study aims at assessing patient preferences to identify key factors influencing psychotherapy choices in Germany. Furthermore, we explore distinct preference patterns within the sample.

Methode: In January 2025, a web survey was administered among adults aged 18-74 with current or previous psychotherapy experience. A two-alternative forced choice discrete choice experiment (DCE) was used to elicit preferences of respondents. Scenarios varied regarding the setting (individual, small group, large group) and delivery mode (face-to-face, digital) of psychotherapy, waiting time (1 month, 5 months, 9 months), gender (female, male) and professional experience of psychotherapist (still in training, less than 5 years, 5 to 10 years, more than 10 years). The DCE was analyzed estimating a random parameters logit model (RPL) that allows for preference heterogeneity. Subsequently, a latent class analysis (LCA) was applied to group patients according to their preferences. Sociodemographic and health-related variables were tested for significant differences across classes using ANOVA and Chi²-tests.

Ergebnisse: The final sample consisted of 1,575 adults ($M_{\text{age}}=47$ years; 70.50% female; 44.38% in current psychotherapy; 66.22% moderate or severe symptoms of depression [PHQ-9]; 48.63% moderate or severe symptoms of anxiety [GAD-7]). The RPL indicated that respondents preferred individual and face-to-face psychotherapy, shorter waiting times, female and more experienced psychotherapists. The relative importance of each attribute was as follows: setting (31.54%), professional experience (24.27%), waiting time (18.00%), delivery mode (16.82%) and therapist gender (9.37%). Preference heterogeneity was observed in all attributes. LCA revealed five preference types, differing in the preferred characteristics (e.g. only one class prefers male psychotherapists) and the evaluation of the relative importance of each attribute (e.g. decision of one specific class is primarily driven by waiting time). Analysis of sociodemographic and health-related factors between classes yielded only slight differences.

Implikation für Forschung und/oder (Versorgungs-)Praxis: Results showed that respondents mainly homogeneously preferred specific treatment characteristics (e.g. individual psychotherapy and more experienced psychotherapists). These preferences should be considered when planning mental health care services and designing innovative treatment formats. Identification of distinct preference types suggest tailored provision of mental health care services.